

Information Needs and Information Usage of the Older Person Club's Members in Bangkok

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Abstract : This research aims to explore the information needs, information usages, and problems of information usage of the older people club's members in Dusit District, Bangkok. There are 12 clubs and 746 club's members in this district. The research results use for older person service in this district. Data is gathered from 252 club's members by using questionnaires. The quantitative approach uses in research by percentage, means and standard deviation. The results are as follows (1) The older people need Information for entertainment, occupation and academic in the field of short story, computer work, and religion and morality. (2) The participants use Information from various sources. (3) The Problem of information usage is their language skills because of the older people's literacy problem.

Keywords : information behavior, older person, information seeking, knowledge discovery and data mining

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